

PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH

ENCYCLOPEDIA OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCES

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SUBJECT: INFORMATION SOURCES AND SERVICES

SUBMITTED TO: PROF. PREETI MAHAJAN

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PREFACE

World War II used the store of accumulated human knowledge as did no other. It has been asserted by some that locating and retrieving existing knowledge and information became a vital key to victory. Many people and considerable sums of money were involved in the task of developing techniques and devices to facilitate the handling of information.

The need and the process were certainly not new. They began with man's earliest efforts to recall and to communicate. As records became more permanent and began to accumulate, the process became more complex, finally calling for specialists to carry it out. From this came library science and the profession of librarianship.

Under the heightened stress of wartime pressures and with the vastly increased store of recorded knowledge, the methods of information control then in use were inadequate to handle the load. New procedures utilizing recently perfected electronic and mechanical devices had to be developed, often by personnel recruited from the user ranks of science or technology. Chemists long concerned with the classification of chemical formulae, botanists trained in taxonomy, mathematicians familiar with the representation of complex matters in symbolic terms, experts in structural linguistics, and engineers experienced in systems development all contributed. From this emerged what is termed information science.

The need for serious attention to the problems of information control and knowledge retrieval continued unabated after the War as research activity mounted in all fields throughout the world. Where were the personnel to do this to be found? The schools of librarianship in Europe and America were teaching a curriculum largely based on procedures, technologies, and institutions established in the 19th and early 20th century. Their graduates were too few in number and, for the large part, inadequately prepared to cope with the needs of the post-war conditions. Yet the basic problems were precisely those, in substance though not in degree, confronted by the library profession through two millennia.

Thus it was that, in 1955, Dean Jesse Shera of the Western Reserve University School of Library Science invited J. H. Perry and one of the present editors to join that institution to establish the first "Center for Documentation and Communication Research."

The waves from that dropped pebble have moved out to cover the world. It was only a matter of time to the instance of a recognized school of library science changing its character and its name to the Graduate School of Library and Information Sciences, as at the University of Pittsburgh in 1963. Similar identifying names are now found at the University of Maryland, School of Library and Information Services; University of Western Ontario, Graduate School of Library and Information Science; University of Sheffield, Postgraduate School of Librarianship and Information Science; and others.

It was also only a matter of time before an enterprising publisher experienced

in the production of major reference works in science and technology would recognize the usefulness of a comprehensive coverage of the broadened field of modern librarianship. The editors, who have a known commitment to a new discipline built upon time-tested foundational principles and incorporating all of the new concepts and techniques, were approached and accepted the challenging opportunity to create a basic compendium of what has become an integrated library and information science. This work is the result.

The editors are equally committed to a "one-world" concept of their science. To this end the approach has been strongly international, as expressed through the composition of the Advisory Board, the choice of contributors, and in the editors' instructions to the contributors.

A more accurate description of the basic editorial policy would be that this work is not so much inter-national as it is non-national, although, admittedly, this has not been easy to accomplish. Nor, indeed, have we been completely successful in conveying this highly sophisticated notion to all contributors equally. But it has been a constant aim.

The emphasis has been, throughout, on depth of treatment. While the contributors were urged to stress basic information, they were likewise encouraged to express their evaluative opinions as well and, wherever possible, to suggest and indicate future trends as they saw them.

This Encyclopedia is arranged in one straight alphabet, as is a dictionary. There are cross references from one heading to another which for one reason or another we preferred to use. The final volume will contain a detailed analytical index to the entire work which is to be used as the principal means of getting into the body of the text. Where appropriate, at the end of the article will be found references to other articles for additional information on the same general topic.

In a work such as this there are many references to individuals both living and deceased. Biographies of many prominent figures in the fields within the scope of the Encyclopedia are included in the regular alphabet. Such biographies are for deceased individuals only.

The editors have frequently found it necessary to turn to their immediate colleagues for counsel and advice on specific points of substance or organization. The following have been particularly helpful and their advice is gratefully acknowledged. Each is a member of the Faculty of the University of Pittsburgh, Graduate School of Library and Information Sciences with but one exception, Dr. Nasser Sharify, who was once a member of the Faculty: Jack Belzer, Jay E. Daily, J. Clement Harrison, Norman Horrocks, William V. Jackson, Frank B. Sessa, Nasser Sharify, C. Walter Stone and Siegfried Treu.

ALLEN KENT
HAROLD LANCOUR

Authority

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- Each article is signed by the contributor.

INTRODUCTION

The **Encyclopedia of Library and Information Science** provides articles on librarianship studies, library science, information science, information technology, information and knowledge organization, and management. The encyclopedia includes articles on everything from traditional library terms to a vocabulary of modern avenues in information science and technology. It is envisioned to become an authoritative source for consultation and reference for any library or information profession related issue and a treasure hub of knowledge on Library and Information Science.

It was **first** published 1968-2003 in 73 volumes under the editorship of Allen Kent, Harold Lancour and Jay E. Daily. **Second edition** edited by Miriam Drake was published 2003 in 4 volumes; **third edition** edited by Marcia J. Bates and Mary Niles Maack came in 2010 in seven volumes.

Fourth edition by John D. McDonald and Michael Levine-Clark came in 2017 also in **seven volumes**.

Scope

- ELIS4 is International as it provides cultural institutions of over 30 countries, which includes a discussion of libraries, archives and museums and also describes the education of professionals working in the libraries.
- The print and eBook publication of 4th edition came in November, 2017. After this, the encyclopedia has not updated or published.
- The ELIS is multivolume reference set which is an authoritative source for consolation and reference for any library or information profession related issue. Thus, ELIS is subject encyclopedia.
- It includes 55 new entries and 60 revised entries, continues to reflect the growing convergence among the disciplines that influence information and the cultural record, with coverage of the latest topics as well as classic articles of historical and theoretical importance.
- The encyclopedia is designed to cover a spectrum of related information disciplines:

Archival Science

Bibliography

Document and Genre Theory

Informatics

Information Systems

Knowledge Management

Library and Information Science

Museum Studies

Records Management

Social Studies of Information

Treatment

- Topical table of contents given in beginning of volume 1 which presents the broad topic areas being listed from first to last, in the order of Ranganathan's P-M-E-S-T.
- Brief introduction of its contributor is given.
- The articles starts with the introduction and ends with the conclusion.
- There is cross references from one heading to another.
For example: ACCOUNTABILITY

See also Personal Accountability

- The articles are explained with the help of examples, tables, diagrams and flow charts.
- It also provides with 'reference and notes' and 'bibliography' at end of each chapter for the additional information on the same general topic.
- 42 articles are marked as ELIS Classic which are of historical or theoretical importance, usually by major individuals in library and information science, which appeared in earlier editions of encyclopedia.
- The final volume contains a detailed analytical index to the entire work which is to be used as the principal means of getting into the body of the text.

Arrangement

- Entries are arranged alphabetically letter by letter.

Format

- Language used in ELIS is English.
- It is available in seven volumes covering in total 435 articles, out of which 42 are ELIS Classics.
- Clear typeface in a two column format signposted by boldface subdivisions and helpful abstracts placed at the beginning of articles.
- Hardcover binding, good quality paper, clear printing.
- ELIS 4th edition is available in **print** and **eBook form**. Users can have the access of the articles at publisher's website <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/e/9781315116143> . It allows users to view-

- 1) Introduction of ELIS 4TH edition
- 2) Table of contents
- 3) Articles with the name of the contributor's (full articles are available for subscriber's only)
- 4) Abstract of articles

Drawbacks

- ELIS is not available in CD-ROM.
- ELIS 4th edition is biased towards the North America and Europe as good coverage has been given to these parts. Whereas, Latin America and near East have been under represented.

Conclusion

There is simply no other work that comes near it in scale or spread for librarians and information specialists it must be regarded as the pre-eminent reference source for the profession. Collections serving institutions where library and information science, museum or archive professionals are trained or undertake research will want to acquire ELIS4. Hence, it is highly recommended to keep library faculty and staff current and should be bought by every research library.

References

Retrieve from (ELIS 4TH edition)

<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/e/9781315116143>

Retrieve from(ELIS 3rd edition)

<https://www.crcpress.com/Encyclopedia-of-Library-and-Information-Sciences/Bates-Maack/p/book/9780849397127>

Retrieve from (Introduction of ELIS 3)

https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://pages.gseis.ucla.edu/faculty/bates/articles/pdf/Introduction.pdf&ved=2ahUKEwjY5Ozr2IrlAhWYfysKHeZUDb0QFjAWegQIAxAB&usq=AOvVaw3q6LS8RbRwqvOh0facl_R8